

Spatiotemporal dynamics of plant diversity and endemism during primary succession on an oceanic-volcanic island

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Abstract

Questions: How does the diversity of native, endemic and alien plant species, as well as the diversity of plant life forms, change during primary succession on lava flows of an oceanic-volcanic island? How do environmental factors such as moisture and soil properties alter diversity during primary succession?

Location: La Palma, Canary Islands.

Methods: We recorded vascular plants and bryophytes in 210 plots on a chronosequence of nine lava flows spanning approx. 6,000 years and covering an elevational range of 1,100 m. In a subset ($n = 78$ plots) we collected and analyzed soil samples for soil nitrogen and plant-available phosphorus. We used generalized linear models, variance partitioning and structural equation models (SEMs) to analyze the data.

Results: Species richness, endemic richness and alien richness increased with time. Natives dominated during early successional stages, whereas endemics and aliens increased with time. At early successional stages, vascular plants and bryophytes had an equal contribution to the species pool, while vascular plants increased up to an 80% contribution at later stages. In the variance partitioning and SEMs, time was the only consistent factor influencing different aspects of diversity during succession (species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism). Only for percent endemism did soil attributes have a substantial impact.

Conclusion: Primary succession on lava flows on La Palma shows a pattern of increasing overall diversity, endemism and alien richness with time. Time is the only factor consistently explaining diversity and endemism, indicating that environmental influences such as climate and soil properties do not substantially alter them during primary succession. Our study contributes to understanding how different facets of diversity assemble through time by using an understudied, yet important island system, and, for the first time, specifically addresses how endemics contribute to the process of primary succession.

KEYWORDS

alien, chronosequence, diversity, endemism, island, lava flow, primary succession, structural equation model, vascular plants

1 | INTRODUCTION

Studying primary succession offers fundamental insights into how plant communities assemble and how diversity is generated through time (Prach & Walker, 2019). On volcanic-oceanic islands (esp. on younger islands), primary succession is one of the most important processes, as these islands are frequently disturbed by ongoing volcanic activity (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007; Whittaker, Triantis, & Ladle, 2008). Primary succession on lava flows is initiated on bare rock surfaces (Walker & del Moral, 2003). Particularly on volcanically active islands, large portions of the island's surface are covered by relatively young substrate. As an example, eruptive material of <500 years age covers around 5% of the surface area of La Palma, Canary Islands (Carracedo, Rodríguez-Badiola, Guillou, De La Nuez, & Pérez Torrado, 2001) and volcanic activity from the last 750 years alone is responsible for about 25% of the surface area of Big Island, Hawaii (Sherrod, Sinton, Watkins, & Brunt, 2007), making primary succession a key process for understanding the distribution of plant life on islands (Cutler, Belyea, & Dugmore, 2008; Turner, Dale, & Everham, 1997; Vitousek, 2002).

As primary succession is a temporal process, time is of major importance for soil development, weathering and soil nutrient availability (esp. nitrogen and phosphorus — Lambers, Raven, Shaver, & Smith, 2008; Vitousek, Walker, Whiteaker, & Matson, 1993). However, temperature differences, for example, along elevational gradients on mountainous islands, have been shown to modify successional processes (Anderson, 2007; del Moral, Sandler, & Muerdter, 2009). Thereby, the question arises whether temperature directly affects succession by governing the rate of biological activity (Anderson-Teixeira, Vitousek, & Brown, 2008) or if temperature indirectly influences primary succession via soil weathering and development processes (Aplet, Hughes, & Vitousek, 1998). Thus, it is likely that thermal modifications of the temporal dynamics of primary succession will alter plant species diversity in a complex, inter-related way.

During succession, functional traits of species contributing to plant communities from different successional stages can change substantially (Clark, Knops, & Tilman, 2019; Craven, Hall, Berlyn, Ashton, & van Breugel, 2018; Korablev, Smirnov, Neshataeva, & Khanina, 2018). Pioneer species must be adapted to harsh environmental conditions such as extreme temperature amplitudes, drought stress, high solar radiation and non-existent soils (Walker & del Moral, 2003) and they must be able to reach the newly formed sites (del Moral & Eckert, 2005). In many cases, bryophytes (and lichens) are the only higher life forms that can tolerate the initial harshness (González-Mancebo, Beltrán Tejera, Losada-Lima, & Sánchez-Pinto, 1996; Mueller-Dombois & Boehmer, 2013) and complex micro-topography (Leutner et al., 2012), while vascular plants tend to establish after micro-climatic and micro-edaphic conditions have been ameliorated (Kitayama, Mueller-Dombois, & Vitousek, 1995). With time, however, vascular plants (especially woody perennial species) often become the dominating life form, following trajectories towards the respective mature surrounding vegetation (González-Mancebo

et al., 1996; Mueller-Dombois & Boehmer, 2013). Thus, we expect to find herbaceous life forms to dominate early successional stages, while woody perennials will increase their importance towards later successional stages.

Oceanic-volcanic islands are famed for their richness of endemic species, mainly resulting from in situ speciation (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007; Whittaker et al., 2008). In fact, as a result of in situ speciation, endemics might be particularly well adapted to such severe but reoccurring disturbances such as lava flows, possibly making endemics well-suited colonists. Recent studies indicate that many endemics on islands prefer newly formed cliff habitats (Irl et al., 2014a), indicating their pre-adaptation to severe disturbances and possibly also their relevance for primary succession. However, disturbances, especially severe ones, are also often associated with the establishment and invasion of non-native species in previously native communities (Hobbs & Huenneke, 1992), with potentially altering effects on species richness, species composition and ultimately also successional trajectories (Potgieter, Wilson, Strasberg, & Richardson, 2014; Vitousek, Walker, Whiteaker, Mueller-Dombois, & Matson, 1987). Although endemics and non-natives are quite different groups of species, we nevertheless expect the importance of both groups to decrease with time as a result of a closing *window of opportunity* for colonization.

Traditionally, the focus of primary succession studies has been on the high elevation islands of the Hawaiian archipelago (especially the recent volcanism of Big Island) as a plethora of studies demonstrates (e.g., Aplet & Vitousek, 1994; Kitayama et al., 1995; Mueller-Dombois & Boehmer, 2013; Waite & Sack, 2011). Surprisingly, only a single study exists for the Canary Islands (González-Mancebo et al., 1996), the arguably best-studied archipelago in the Atlantic Ocean, even though recent volcanic activity is ongoing and well documented for several islands (Tenerife, Lanzarote, El Hierro, La Palma; Carracedo et al., 2002), as is the case for other archipelagos (Marchese & Grillo, 2000; Tagawa, 1992; Tsuyuzaki, 2009). Here, we want to reduce this geographic imbalance on island succession studies by investigating primary succession on La Palma, Canary Islands. We therefore study different aspects of diversity and endemism during primary succession by using a chronosequence of nine recent lava flows (max. age 6,000 years) on this subtropical and, in parts, semi-arid island. First, we investigate how plant species diversity changes with time. Second, we determine if endemics and aliens can use a *window of opportunity* (DeGasperis & Motzkin, 2007) during primary succession in order to contribute to diversity. A window of opportunity for the colonization of endemics or the invasion of aliens can establish during certain time periods of succession, when biotic and abiotic conditions meet the environmental requirements of the species and thus allow successful establishment and recruitment (sensu DeGasperis & Motzkin, 2007). Third, we investigate how plant life form diversity changes during primary succession. Fourth, we test if environmental factors such as climate and soil properties directly and indirectly alter plant diversity during primary succession.

FIGURE 1 Map of the study area. (a) The southern part of La Palma island situated within the Canary Islands archipelago. (b) Age of each lava flow used in this study (red) and location of sampling plots. Blue Xs mark each elevational level sampled that consists of three plots per elevational level. (c) Elevational range sampled on each lava flow using 100 m intervals [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Study area

About 420 km off the coast of North Africa, La Palma (area of 706 km²) is the northwestern-most island of the Canary Islands archipelago (Figure 1a). The Canary Islands, including La Palma, are a biodiversity hotspot and are recognized for their many iconic endemic species (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007). The southern part of the island is characterized by recent and historic volcanic activity. Here we find several historically dated lava flows (i.e., lava flows dated by Spanish and Castilian chronicles) as well as many older eruptions (Carracedo et al., 2001). Most lava flows originate on the flanks of the so-called Cumbre Vieja ridge (max. ~2,000 m a.s.l.), which dissects the southern part of the island from north to south (Figure 1b). Flowing downward towards the ocean, the lava flows cover a substantial elevational gradient.

Within our study area on the subtropical island of La Palma (~28° N), the climate is mild and dry to moderately humid, ranging from 19 to 14.5°C mean annual temperature (MAT) and from around 250 mm/a to more than 900 mm/a mean annual precipitation (MAP; Irl & Beierkuhnlein, 2011). With increasing elevation, temperatures decrease while precipitation increases. At the highest elevations of our study area (~1,200 m a.s.l.) MAT averages at 14°C and MAP 910 mm/a, which results in more temperate-humid conditions. Distinct vegetation units directly follow the climate gradients in our study area (del Arco Aguilar, González-González, Garzón-Machado, & Pizarro-Hernández, 2010), which are transected by the lava flows. Halophytic communities inhabit the coastal zone, whereas a succulent scrub occupies the lower elevations (up to 500 m a.s.l.). With increasing elevation (between 500 and 800 m a.s.l.), a low elevation broom scrub becomes the dominant vegetation unit. The Canary Pine forest is found above 800 m a.s.l.

2.2 | Sampling design and study species

Volcanic activity and the age of lava flows can be precisely dated (e.g., using historic records or radio-isotope methods); thus, an accurate chronosequence can be established, which serves as a base for a space-for-time approach (Walker, Wardle, Bardgett, & Clarkson, 2010). La Palma offers a good example of a chronosequence of nine recent lava flows, ranging from about 40 to around 6,000 years of age (Carracedo et al., 2002) and spanning strong elevational, and temperature gradients (i.e., between 100 and 1,200 m). Thus, the island is optimally suited as a model system to study primary succession on subtropical oceanic islands. To keep samples comparable throughout the whole sampling area, we only sampled sites on lava flows with *a'a*-lava (the dominant type of lava in the study area), whereas we excluded *pahoehoe*-lava (rare) as well as areas of tephra.

We recorded all plant species, that is, vascular plants (spermatophytes and pteridophytes) and bryophytes, in 4 m × 4 m plots at 100 m intervals from 100 to 1,200 m a.s.l. However, we were unable to sample all elevational levels on all lava flows due to specific

restrictions, for example, spatial extent of the lava flows, access restrictions to private property, cultivation or lava flows covered by tephra (Figure 1c). In accordance with the guidelines for optimal sampling for field studies (Schweiger, Irl, Steinbauer, Dengler, & Beierkuhnlein, 2016), three replicates were recorded at each elevational level within a lava flow. At each elevation, plot location was randomly selected with the constraint that each plot had to be located >30 m from the lava flow edge (to reduce possible edge effects) and at least 30 m from all other plots. Sampling took place in February 2014 and March/April 2016.

Species status (i.e., non-endemic native, endemic to the Canary Islands and alien) is defined according to Acebes Ginovés et al. (2010) for spermatophytes and pteridophytes and Lima, Dirkse, Rodríguez Núñez, and González Mancebo (2010) for bryophytes. An expert in bryophytes (Eduard Hertel, Ecological Botanical Garden, University of Bayreuth) was consulted for species not identified with certainty. On La Palma, both alien richness and endemic richness generally decrease with elevation (Steinbauer et al., 2017), while rare endemics aggregate at higher elevations (Irl et al., 2017).

Besides total species richness, we calculated different richness values depending on the species' status (endemic, alien) or plant life forms (trees, shrubs, herbs, grasses, ferns, mosses). We divided all subordinate richness values by total species richness, respectively. This results in percent non-endemic natives, percent endemics, percent aliens as well as percentage values for every plant life form. Percentages are better suited to identify the relative importance of a specific species group within a community because they are corrected for richness differences between communities (Irl et al., 2015).

2.3 | Environmental variables

We extracted precise lava flow ages (i.e., the variable *time*) from the geologic literature (Carracedo et al., 2001). We took MAT and MAP from a climate model calculated for La Palma by Irl et al. (2015). We extracted elevation values from a digital elevation model (2 m × 2 m resolution) provided by the Consejería de Cabildo Insular de La Palma.

2.4 | Soil analysis

For a subset of plots, we took three soil samples close to the plot edges. All three plot samples were mixed, sieved to 2-mm fractions and air-dried in paper bags. For soil nutrient analysis, samples of three plots per lava flow age and elevation were mixed, resulting in 78 soil samples. This procedure allowed us to estimate average soil nutrient composition per lava flow age and elevation while substantially reducing lab and labour expenses.

Total N concentration was measured with a CHN element analyser (Flash-EA 1112, Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). For extraction of PO₄³⁻, we used the Bray-1 method as described by Khan and Joergensen (2012). 40 ml of Bray-1 solution was added to 8 g ± 0.01 g of 2 mm sieved and air-dried soil (1 soil [g] per 5 Bray-1 [ml]). To account for absorption during the treatment,

duplicate samples for intermediate elevations were treated with a spike of $25 \mu\text{g PO}_4^{3-} \text{g}^{-1}$ soil. All samples were then shaken for 30 min and filtered with a cellulose fluted filter. Additional centrifuging was applied to samples that remained cloudy. Measurements were carried out photometrically with a FIAcompact autosampler (MLE, Dresden, Germany). Absorbed P was calculated via $1 - (\text{PO}_4^{3-} \text{ spike sample} - \text{PO}_4^{3-} \text{ unspiked sample})/25$ and added as a proxy to all measurements of the corresponding lava age class.

2.5 | Statistics

In a first step, we tested all environmental variables for collinearity following the select07 method described by Dormann et al. (2013). Elevation, MAT and MAP were highly correlated. Therefore, we continued all analyses using only elevation because it integrates climatic variables such as MAT and MAP (Körner, 2007). Then, we tested univariate relationships between diversity indices and time using generalized linear models (GLMs) based on transformations for best model fit. Tested transformations were logarithmic, quadratic (x^2) and quadratic binomial ($x + x^2$). We used the AIC to identify the best model fit. For the GLMs we used a Poisson distribution for richness data and for percent data a binomial distribution based on a two-column integer matrix of success and failure values per plot. For example, a percent endemism value of 10% could consist of one endemic species (= one success) and nine non-endemic native species (= nine failures). For all GLMs, Nagelkerke's R^2 was calculated as goodness-of-fit measure using the R package *fmsb* (R Core Team, 2018).

Second, we used variance partitioning based on multiple linear regression models (*varpart*; Legendre, 2008) to identify the joint and independent contribution of explanatory variables to explaining species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism in our system. Thus, the variable *time* consists of the lava flow age, while the variable *climate* consists of elevation (which stands for the resource availability of temperature/energy and precipitation/water). The variable *soil* combines plant-available phosphorus and soil nitrogen – two essential soil nutrients during primary succession (Kitayama et al., 1995; Lambers et al., 2008). Because soil samples were taken only for a subset of plots, the variance partitioning was applied to the full data set using all plots ($n = 210$) and a subset of plots where soil data was available ($n = 78$). We also ran the variance partitioning on the subset data using only time and climate to evaluate if the subset data were representative of the full data set. All functions are implemented in the R package *vegan*. Significance levels are defined as follows: * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$ and *** $p < 0.001$.

In a third step, we built structural equation models (SEMs) based on a conceptual path dependency model (see Figure 4a below) to assess interdependencies between climate, temporal dynamics and soil properties. SEMs have the advantage that they are able to account for direct and indirect effects of predicting variables (i.e., environmental conditions) on studied responses (Grace et al., 2012; Sonne et al., 2016). Our conceptual path dependency model assumes that time and climate can either affect richness and endemism directly or indirectly via soil properties. To include soil into the SEMs, again the

subset was used where soil data were available ($n = 78$). All SEMs were implemented in the R package *lavaan*, which lets the user create individual links between variables and then calculates (a) a standardized model estimate (that can be seen as a correlation coefficient) per linkage as well as a p -value, and (b) an R^2 value for all dependent variables. A full SEM was calculated for each response variable (species richness, endemic richness, percent endemism) including all predefined links from the conceptual path dependency model. The resulting graphs show all significant links as defined by the model output, while non-significant links are displayed as grey dashed lines. To improve SEM fit, we tested untransformed variables as well as logarithmic and quadratic transformations for all explanatory variables.

3 | RESULTS

3.1 | General results

We recorded 146 species in 210 plots on nine lava flows of La Palma spanning approximately a 6,000-year chronosequence. Of these, 131 were vascular plant species and 15 were bryophytes. With regard to species status, we recorded 98 non-endemic natives, 44 endemics, ten alien species (of which the most dominant were: 44 occurrences of *Ageratina adenophora*, 14 occurrences of *Opuntia maxima*, nine occurrences of *Pennisetum setaceum* and seven occurrences of *Mercurialis annua*) and nine species that could not be identified to the species level and therefore could not be assigned a definitive status when following the main sources of nomenclature (Acebes Ginovés et al., 2010; Lima et al., 2010). Species richness per plot ranged from 0 to 41 species with highest species richness found on the third oldest lava flow (2,000 years) at around 600 m elevation.

3.2 | Biotic modifiers of primary succession with regard to species status and life forms

Species richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.68$, $p < 0.001$) and endemic richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.49$, $p < 0.001$) increased with time (Figure 2a). Although only few aliens were present (maximum alien richness per plot = 4), a significant positive richness–time relationship was detected for alien richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.28$, $p < 0.001$). The percent non-endemic natives showed a negative relationship with time (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.16$, $p < 0.001$), whereas the percent endemism had a hump-shaped relationship with time (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.17$, $p < 0.001$; maximum ~40% at around 3,500 years; Figure 2b). percent aliens increased significantly with time (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.13$, $p = 0.0003$).

Both vascular plant species richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.72$, $p < 0.001$) and bryophyte richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.05$, $p = 0.006$) showed an increase with time (Figure 2c). Within vascular plants, tree richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.19$, $p < 0.001$), shrub richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.45$, $p < 0.001$), herb richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.47$, $p < 0.001$) and fern richness (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.17$, $p < 0.001$) showed an increase with time while grass richness did not show any significant relationship (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.02$, $p = 0.079$).

FIGURE 2 Temporal dependency of different diversity measures. Time vs species status as (a) richness values and (b) percentages. Time vs life forms as (c) richness values and as (d) percentages. Lines indicate significant correlations, whereas dashed lines represent non-significant relationships. Bands are shown to indicate 95% confidence intervals instead of raw data points to increase readability. Nagelkerke's R^2 values for GLMs and significance levels are shown in the respective legends. *, ** and *** represent significance levels of $p < 0.05$, $p < 0.01$ and $p < 0.001$, respectively. Note that standard binomial functions (i.e., $x^2 + x$) appear skewed in log-space [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

The percentage of plant life forms as an indicator of life form contribution to the plant community expressed a different pattern with time (Figure 2d). The percent of vascular plants (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.27$, $p < 0.001$), percent herbs (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.06$, $p = 0.003$) and percent trees (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.12$, $p = 0.0006$) increased, while percent bryophytes decreased (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.27$, $p < 0.001$). The percent grasses expressed a U-shaped relationship with time with a minimum around 3,500 years (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.08$, $p = 0.009$). The percent shrubs showed a hump-shaped relationship with time with a maximum around 4,000 years (Nagelkerke's $R^2 = 0.23$, $p < 0.001$).

3.3 | Abiotic modifiers of plant diversity and endemism during primary succession

The multiple linear regression model for the full data set ($n = 210$) on which the variance partitioning is based explained more than 40% of the variance for species richness ($R^2 = 0.42$, $p < 0.001$; Figure 3a), 37% for endemic richness ($R^2 = 0.37$, $p < 0.001$) and 21% for percent endemism ($R^2 = 0.21$, $p < 0.001$). For species richness, time (i.e., lava flow age) and climate (i.e., elevation) had similarly large relative contributions to explained variance with a smaller joint contribution. For both endemic richness and percent endemism, time was the major relative contributor to explained variance followed by climate and the joint contribution.

Including soil (i.e., soil nitrogen and plant-available phosphorus) into the variance partitioning using the subset that also had soil data

($n = 78$) showed a different picture (Figure 3b). The multiple linear regression model that the variance partitioning is based on explained 44% of the variance for species richness ($R^2 = 0.44$, $p < 0.001$), 40% for endemic richness ($R^2 = 0.40$, $p < 0.001$) and 30% for percent endemism ($R^2 = 0.30$, $p < 0.001$). For species richness, time was the most important relative contributor, while climate and time + climate + soil contributed to a lesser extent. For endemic richness, time was of overwhelming importance with minor contributions by soil and climate + soil. For percent endemism, soil ended up being the most important contributor to explained variance followed by time, climate and time + climate + soil.

We ran the variance partitioning for the subset data using only time and climate to evaluate if the subset was representative of the full data set (Appendix S1). The results did not differ qualitatively for species richness and endemic richness. For percent endemism, both time and climate were non-significant, so the variance partitioning could not be executed.

3.4 | Direct and indirect effects of climate, time and soil on diversity and endemism

A hierarchical path dependency model, illustrated in Figure 4a, was implemented in the SEMs. Thereby, time and climate can directly influence the response variables (species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism) or indirectly via soil nitrogen or plant-available phosphorus. Only time directly influenced species richness positively (Figure 4b), while all other explanatory variables had

FIGURE 3 Variance partitioning of (a) environmental variables time and climate as explanatory variables for species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism ($n = 210$) and (b) environmental variables time, climate and soil as explanatory variables for species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism using a subset ($n = 78$). Soil is a grouped environmental variable consisting of plant-available phosphorus and soil nitrogen. Boxes indicate the relative contribution of the explained variance covered by each explanatory variable independently and by two or more explanatory variables jointly. In (b) 'Other' stands for the combinations Soil + Age and Soil + Climate. However, both combinations reach relative contributions of $>3\%$ and were therefore not displayed separately. R^2 values denote the total explained variance resulting from the respective multiple linear regression models. For details on how the grouped environmental variables were established see the Material and Methods section [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

non-significant direct relationships with species richness. Both climate (elevation) and time had a negative influence on plant-available phosphorus, with climate's influence being much stronger, whereas time had a positive influence on soil nitrogen. For endemic richness (Figure 4c) we see a similar pattern as for species richness. Only time directly influenced endemic richness positively with all other variables having a non-significant influence on endemic richness. Time and climate (represented by elevation) had a negative influence on plant-available phosphorus with climate's influence being much stronger, while time had a positive influence on soil nitrogen. For percent endemism (Figure 4d) the picture changes slightly. Time and plant-available phosphorus had a direct positive influence on percent endemism. Climate had a strong negative influence on plant-available phosphorus and time had a weak positive influence on soil nitrogen.

4 | DISCUSSION

4.1 | Spatiotemporal dynamics of diversity and endemism during primary succession

Primary succession on recent La Palma lava flows shows a distinctive temporal pattern concerning diversity and endemism, with environmental factors substantially altering all patterns. We highlight three key findings. First, species richness, endemic richness and alien richness all increase with time, while their relative contributions to successional communities show a more complex pattern. At the onset of primary succession, native non-endemic species dominate, whereas with advancing succession endemics and aliens become more common. This demonstrates that the *window of opportunity* (DeGasperi

& Motzkin, 2007) for both endemics and aliens to establish is during later successional stages, and not during pioneer and mid-successional stages. Second, bryophytes and vascular plants have a similar contribution at the pioneer stages. However, at later successional stages the contribution of vascular plants to the community increases, which is mainly driven by a disproportional increase in shrubs and herbs. Thus, mature communities are dominated by woody species and perennial herbs. Third, time and climate both influence species richness equally, whereas time is more important than climate as a driver of endemism. However, the SEMs illustrate that time is the only variable that consistently influences species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism. Surprisingly, climate and soil properties do not have any direct influence on species richness and endemic richness, although these factors strongly affect species composition. Only for percent endemism do we see a direct influence of plant-available phosphorus in addition to time – a result that is also reflected in the variance partitioning. At least for our study system, time, climate and soil are connected by complex interactions, while time is the only consistent factor generating different facets of diversity and endemism during primary succession.

4.2 | Temporal patterns of diversity and endemism

Species richness strongly increases with time during primary succession on lava flows on La Palma. This is a consistent pattern found throughout primary and secondary succession in a wide range of different study systems (e.g., Cutler, 2010; del Moral & Magnússon, 2014; del Moral, Saura, & Emenegger, 2010; Magnússon, Magnússon, Ólafsson, & Sigurdsson, 2014). Initial harsh environmental conditions select rigorously for a small group

FIGURE 4 Structural equation models (SEMs) for explaining species richness, endemic richness and percent endemism using a subset of the dataset ($n = 78$). (a) Conceptual representation of the SEM showing the structural hierarchy as well as all links defined in the model. SEMs for (b) species richness, (c) endemic richness, and (d) percent endemism using the same hierarchical framework. Blue arrows show significant positive, red significant negative relationships. The width of the arrows is proportional to the standardized estimate given next to each arrow. Grey arrows indicate non-significant relationships. R^2 values are given for all response variables. To improve model fit, some explanatory variables were either log-transformed or x^2 -transformed [Colour figure can be viewed at wileyonlinelibrary.com]

of highly adapted but widespread species. However, with time, environmental conditions are ameliorated, enabling more and more species to establish. Other types of primary succession, for example, on glacial till, often show a peak in species richness (Dolezal et al., 2008; Jones & del Moral, 2005). This highlights that the type of primary succession might influence how species assemble through time. In fact, a quantitative comparison of successional dynamics across succession types, taxonomic groups and biogeographic regions might be a promising step forward for succession ecology.

Endemic richness and percent endemism tended to increase with time, indicating that endemics, which were mainly vascular plants, followed the overall richness pattern. Consequently, our results highlight that endemics are not particularly well-suited as pioneer species on lava flows. Thus, the so-called 'lavacolous' species typically found in the initial stages of succession on lava flows of the Canary Islands mentioned by Juan et al. (2000) mainly constitute more widespread non-endemic species that are nevertheless adapted to the very harsh pioneer conditions. Nonetheless, endemics occurred throughout all successional stages, indicating their important contribution during primary succession. However, it needs to be further investigated whether the continuous presence of volcanic activity and conditions associated with primary succession on the island and the whole archipelago have influenced speciation processes leading

to the evolution of endemic species. Nevertheless, endemics on La Palma have been shown to profit from virgin cliff habitats where primary succession is initiated, for example, after the construction of roads (Irl et al., 2014a). However, such roadside cliff habitats protect endemics from introduced herbivores (Irl et al., 2014a), which preferentially feed on endemics (Cubas et al., 2019). Selective browsing by introduced herbivores might alter patterns of endemics in primary succession (Cubas et al., 2018; Irl et al., 2014b) but to what degree remains unknown.

Aliens were virtually absent from primary succession on lava flows of La Palma, which stands in contrast to studies from Hawaii (where aliens are associated with disturbances; Aplet & Vitousek, 1994; Aplet et al., 1998), La Réunion (where aliens have been shown to alter successional trajectories; Potgieter et al., 2014) or Mount Pinatubo (where ~60% of the species are aliens; Marler & del Moral, 2011). Again, the already harsh conditions found on lava flows (high solar radiation, high maximum temperatures, non-existent soils; Walker & del Moral, 2003) in combination with the dry conditions (~260 mm/a at low elevations) likely constitute a major pre-selecting filter for the establishment of aliens. All ten aliens recorded in this study are generalist invaders found in a variety of different habitats and environmental conditions around the world. Also, the alien species pool is relatively small on La Palma and the Canary Islands in general compared to the aforementioned islands (Kueffer et al.,

2010), decreasing the overall probability of aliens being adapted to primary succession conditions.

4.3 | Temporal patterns of plant life forms

Plant life forms display a consistent successional pattern on lava flows on La Palma. Bryophytes and vascular plants (together with globally dispersed lichens specialized to pioneer stages such as *Stereocaulon vesuvianum*; González-Mancebo et al., 1996) dominate the earliest successional stages, both contributing about 50% of species. In later successional stages, vascular plants become more important, reaching a contribution of around 80% on the oldest lava flows – a typical pattern for primary succession on lava flows (Ah-Peng et al., 2007; Cutler, 2010; Korabiev et al., 2018) and primary succession in general (Walker & del Moral, 2003).

Shrubs and herbs are the main life forms of vascular plants at later successional stages. This is typical for the mature ecosystems found on La Palma surrounding the studied lava flows (i.e., succulent scrub, broom scrub and the Canary Pine forest). These ecosystems, especially the succulent scrub and the broom scrub, are dominated by perennial shrubs and herbs (e.g., *Euphorbia lamarckii*, *Echium breviflorum*, *Retama rhodorhizoides* or *Rumex lunaria*; del Arco Aguilar et al., 2010). The Canary Pine forest on the leeward side of the island is almost completely dominated by a single pine species in the tree layer (*Pinus canariensis*), while various herbs and shrubs occur in the undergrowth (e.g. *Lotus campylocladus* subsp. *hillebrandii*, *Cistus symphytifolius* or *Adenocarpus foliolosus*; Hoffmann et al., 2018). With time, the influence of the surrounding (mature) communities likely becomes increasingly important as propagule sources for the lava flows, often leading to successional trajectories converging towards the surrounding communities (Prach et al., 2016; Rolim, Machado, & Pillar, 2017).

4.4 | Interactions and feedbacks between time, climate and soil

When looking at different aspects of diversity, time is the only consistent influence on primary succession dynamics in our study system. This is confirmed by the variance partitioning as well as the path analyses (SEMs) although they are based on quite different statistical approaches. However, the path analyses show that both time and climate jointly and interactively govern soil formation and development processes, which is also found in other successional studies (Clark et al., 2019; Kitayama et al., 1995). Remarkably, in both the SEM and the variance partitioning for the subset including soil data, soil nutrients such as nitrogen and phosphorus that are generally considered fundamental resources for plant life (Lambers et al., 2008) seem to have little effect on species richness and endemic richness – two important measures of diversity on oceanic islands (Whittaker & Fernández-Palacios, 2007). This might be a result of the harsh, in parts arid, conditions on the southern part of La Palma where the sampled lava flows are located. Water deficiency prevalent on these sites might override soil nutrients as a driver of

diversity because often the most limiting factor drives the overall pattern in a system (cf. Liebig, 1840).

In the SEMs, plant-available phosphorus has a positive influence on percent endemism, i.e., communities where endemics are important are rich in phosphorus. To a certain degree, this can also be inferred from the variance partitioning that uses the subset including soil data. The plant-available phosphorus–percent endemism relationship is likely an indirect effect of elevation. Both plant-available phosphorus and percent endemism decrease with elevation, leading to a positive plant-available phosphorus–percent endemism relationship. This relationship suggests that endemic plant species on La Palma do not cope well with very nutrient-limited conditions (e.g., very early successional stages), but rather establish at more mature stages.

Successional dynamics are exceptionally slow on La Palma with regard to its latitudinal position (Anderson, 2007). Even after more than half a millennium of succession vegetation did not form closed-canopy stands. For example, while surrounded by mature stands of densely forested Canary Pine forest, the medium-aged lava flow (534 years) only supported very few and poorly growing pine trees. Not until later does mature pine forest develop on lava flows on the island. Indeed, mature, closed-canopy forest can establish after only a few decades on other islands, for example, La Réunion (Potgieter et al., 2014), Hawaii (Kitayama et al., 1995), Miyake-Jima (Japan; Kamijo et al., 2002) or Krakatau (Whittaker, 1989). In contrast to the rather dry conditions, especially at lower elevations, on the leeward side of the Canary Islands (Garzón-Machado, Otto, & del Arco Aguilar, 2014), humid-tropical or humid-temperate conditions characterize the studied lava flows of all aforementioned islands (c.f. Prach & Walker, 2019). This ubiquitous availability of water, in combination with mild to warm temperatures, leads to an adaptive cycle between vegetation and soil (i.e., fast establishment of plants due to favorable moisture conditions initiate accelerating soil development, which in turn allows more plants to establish, and so on; Anderson-Teixeira et al., 2008; Cutler, 2011). In drought-prone systems, such as the leeward side of the Canary Islands, stress levels are high as a result of unfavorable growing conditions on bare volcanic rock, leading to a reduction in successional dynamics by several orders of magnitude.

5 | CONCLUSION

Primary succession on lava flows on the subtropical island of La Palma shows a clear pattern of increasing diversity and endemism with time. Thereby, the spatiotemporal pattern of diversity and endemism is, to a certain degree, altered by environmental conditions such as climate and soil. Our study illustrates how different facets of diversity are generated and assembled with time. Understanding how this happens is key to deciphering the general dynamics of species assembly. Thus, lava flows are distinct spatiotemporal entities that are often replicated in space and time. Following suggestions made by Prach and Walker (2019), future studies could combine different study sites (e.g., along a latitudinal/biogeographic gradient) using a

quasi-experimental, highly standardized study system (i.e., lava flows) to help understand the underlying drivers generating diversity in plant communities in a large-scale or even global spatiotemporal context.

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AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

S.D.H.I conceived the ideas; T.P., S.H., H.H., S.D.H.I. and A.J. collected the data; S.D.H.I. analyzed the data; S.D.H.I. and A.H.S. led the writing with all co-authors contributing. All authors gave their final approval for publication.

DATA AVAILABILITY

All soil data can be accessed in Appendix S2.

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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information may be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of the article.

Appendix S1. Variance partitioning of the subset data using time and climate only

Appendix S2. Full soil data set used in this study

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